

Low Latency of Shift Register Design using Quantum Dot Cellular Automata

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ABSTRACT

Quantum Dot Cellular Automata (QCA) offer an alternative to CMOS technology for designing sequential circuits. The paper focuses on optimizing D flip-flops and JK flip-flops to design a serial in serial out shift register. The QCA-based circuits are used in the computational Nano hardware to present computations at ultra-high speed. A systematic approach has been utilized to design the serial-in-serial-out shift register using JK flip-flop and D flip-flop. These flip-flops were initially designed with lower complexity which is the dominant factor for designing any complex sequential circuit. This design leverages the unique properties of QCA, like high density and low power consumption, to achieve efficient data shifting. The QCA based designs have been validated and subjected to simulation using the QCA Designer tool ver. 2.0.3.

Keywords: QCA, SISO- Serial in serial out shift register, D Flip-flop, JK flip-flop

1.INTRODUCTION

Quantum-dot cellular automata (QCA) is one of the new nanoelectronics that has emerged in the last decade. QCA technology was first introduced by Lent et al. in 1993 [1]. QCA is being used as a new technique for computation. QCA is a good choice as a replacement for CMOS technology due to many aspects such as its ultra-high speed, small size, and low power consumption. It depends on electron configurations instead of voltage levels as in CMOS. The key issue in QCA is complexity reduction. Many papers have been presented on designing important digital circuits using QCA technology. Most of these papers were searching

for an optimal form. Researchers have been paying attention to the design of the memory cell as one of the important circuits in QCA technology [2], and a well-optimized flip-flop structure [3-5], in addition to register circuits. The presented flip-flop was used to carry out many register circuits.

In QCA technology, researchers look for optimization in terms of area, delay, and cells required. As such, optimization of the brick units is a very essential issue. To have better sight of view the significance of QCA compared to CMOS technology is highlighted by several critical quantitative metrics. For instance, QCA can achieve operational speeds exceeding 1 THz, which is

substantially higher than the maximum clock frequency of around 10 GHz typically observed in advanced CMOS circuits [3,4]. In terms of power efficiency, QCA operates about hundreds of times better than low power CMOS methods. Furthermore, QCA offers a remarkable density of over 1 billion cells per square centimeter, significantly surpassing the approximately 100 million transistors per square centimeter that CMOS technology can achieve. These quantitative differences not only emphasize the potential of QCA for future high-performance computing applications but also illustrate its advantages in power efficiency and scalability, making it a compelling alternative to traditional CMOS technology. Therefore, in this paper new designs for shift register will be proposed using QCA nanotechnology.

2. BASICS OF QCA:

A QCA device consists of a collection of QCA cells [6]. Each QCA cell has two electrons and four electron-wells. The behavior of electrons inside a QCA cell is determined by the Schrodinger equation using a quantum-mechanical hamiltonian [7, 8]. The coulomb coupling between electrons defines the binary value of a QCA cell and the automata between neighboring cells. The fundamental logic components for QCA implementation are the majority gate and inverter. The majority gate has four I/O terminal cells— three input terminals and one output terminal as visualized. Majority gate can be used to implement the AND and OR logic functions. Through the various combinations of the majority and inverter gates, QCA logic can be used to define a complete logic function [9] system. For QCA devices, synchronization is necessary not only to ensure proper timing but also to define functionality. By assigning clock phases to different inputs of a QCA device, the direction of data flow (thus computation) can be manipulated [6]. The implementation of clocking is performed through clock wires buried underneath the layer on which the QCA cells are placed [10] as shown in Fig. 1. CMOS clocking is implemented adiabatically in order to reduce power dissipation. Adiabatic switching is performed by generating electric fields over QCA cells to drive a clock zone to the ground state, where logic values are nullified without complete electrical discharge [7].

Fig: Architecture of QCA a) Single Layer b) Multi-Layer c) Opposite Layer

3. METHODOLOGY

The design a shift register using Quantum-dot Cellular Automata (QCA), primarily need to construct a series of interconnected QCA cells, where each cell represents a single bit, and the arrangement of these cells allows data to shift from one cell to the next based on a clock signal, typically achieved by utilizing the fundamental building block of a QCA majority gate to create D flip-flops which are then cascaded to form the shift register; this arrangement enables serial data transfer by shifting the bits one position at a time. A shift register is a type of digital circuit that is used to store and shift a series of binary data. It can be designed using various types of flip flop circuits, however JK flip-flop-based shift registers have several benefits over other types of shift registers which include: Universal operation -The JK flip-flop can be used in different modes, such as S-R, T, and D flip-flops, which makes it versatile in applications. High speed operation- JK flip-flops have a faster operation.

Shift Registers have also been designed using D Flip Flops in this paper, focus has been on designing JK Flip Flop based Shift registers. Performance parameters of various proposed models are compared for JK Flip Flop and the 4-bit Shift Register with the existing designs are given in Table respectively. The JK Flip Flop design presented in this paper is seen to have less number of cells in the layout and very low QCA cost.

The essential building block in the shift register is D Flip-flop. The D Flip-flop is designed using the majority gate in Quantum Dot Cellular Automata Technology. Connect the D input to the desired data bit, and use the clock signal to control the state transition of the flip-flop. And cascading the flip-flops are connected between output of one D flip-flop to the D input of the next flip-flop in series. The data will shift through the chain when the clock signal is applied, moving one bit position at a time. When routing QCA wires, utilize techniques like coplanar or multilayer crossovers to manage wire intersections without affecting the data transmission.

4. SIMULATION RESULTS:

Fig: 4-Bit Serial in serial out shift register with D Flip-flop

Fig: Simulation waveform of 4-Bit Serial in serial out shift register with D Flip-flop

Fig: 4-Bit Serial in parallel out shift register with D Flip-flop

Fig: Simulation waveform for 4-Bit Serial in parallel out shift register with D Flip-flop

Fig: 4-Bit Parallel in parallel out shift register with D Flip-flop

Fig: Simulation waveform for 4-Bit Parallel in parallel out shift register with D- Flip-flop

From the simulated waveforms of various shift registers such as serial in serial out shift register, serial in parallel out shift register and parallel in parallel out shift register are observed. And the performance metrics such as cell count, Latency and Average and total energy dissipation values are calculated. The following table shows the comparative analysis between three shift registers are designed using D Flip-flops.

Circuit Name	Cell Count	Total Area (μm ²)	Latency	Average Energy Dissipation	Total Energy Dissipation
4-bit SISO (JK)	216	0.19	1	0.248 eV	0.743 eV
4 bit SISO (D)	129	0.1	1	0.308 eV	0.759 eV
4-bit SIPO (D)	199	0.128	6	0.291 eV	0.759 eV
4-bit PIPO (D)	114	0.957	1	0.156 eV	0.582 eV

5. CONCLUSION:

This paper presents a QCA based JK Flip Flop design that is highly efficient, and proposes Shift Registers that utilize this D Flip Flop design. The proposed designs can be easily scaled up to accommodate larger N-bits. Thus verified the effectiveness of these designs, simulations were conducted using the QCA Designer simulation tool, and the layouts and operations were found to be successful. There is a significant reduction in cell count, area, latency, and the cost of our proposed logic using D flip-flops.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

- [1] Seyedi S. et al. Design and evaluation of a new structure for fault-tolerance full-adder based on quantum-dot cellular automata, Nano communications and networks, 2018.
- [2] Jun-Cheol Jeon, "Low-complexity QCA universal shift register design using multiplexer and D flip-flop based on electronic correlations", The Journal of Supercomputing, vol. 76, pp. 6438-6452, 2021.
- [3] Mohammad Mudakir Fazili, Mohsin Fayaz Shah, Syed Farah Naz and Ambika Prasad Shah, "Survey taxonomy and methods of QCA-based design techniques: digital circuits", IOP Science Semiconductor Science and Technology, 2022, [online] Available: <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6641/ac5ec0>.
- [4] T N Sasamal, A K Singh and A Mohan, Quantum-Dot Cellular Automata Based Digital Logic Circuits: A Design Perspective, Singapore:Springer, vol. 879, 2020, [online] Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-1823-2>.
- [5] Baljot Kaur and Rajesh Mehra, "CMOS Design Analysis of 4 Bit Shifters", International Journal for Research in Engineering Application & Management (IJREAM), vol. 04, no. 03, June 2018.
- [6] M. T. Niemier and P. M. Kogge, "Problems in designing with QCAs: Layout = timing", Int. J. Circ.Theor. Appl, vol. 29, pp. 49-62, 2001.
- [7] CS Lent, PD Tougaw, W Porod and GH Bernstein, "Quantum cellular automata", Nanotechnology, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 49-57, 1993.
- [8] Ahmed, S.; Naz, S.F.; Sharma, S.; Ko, S.B. Design of quantum-dot cellular automata-based communication system using modular N-bit binary to gray and gray to binary converters. Int. J. Commun. Syst. 2020, 34, e4702
- [9] Bilal, B.; Ahmed, S.; Kakkar, V. An insight into beyond CMOS next generation computing using quantum-dot cellular automata nanotechnology. Int. J. Eng. Manuf. 2018, 8, 25.
- [10] Ganesh, E.; Kishore, L.; Rangachar, M. Implementation of Quantum cellular automata combinational and sequential circuits using Majority logic reduction method. Int. J. Nanotechnol. Appl. 2008, 2, 89-106.
- [11] Wolkow, R.A.; Livadaru, L.; Pitters, J.; Taucer, M.; Piva, P.; Salomons, M.; Cloutier, M.; Martins, B.V. Silicon atomic quantum dots enable beyond-CMOS electronics. In Field-Coupled Nanocomputing; Springer: Berlin/Heidelberg, Germany, 2014; pp. 33-58.
- [12] Huang, J.; Momenzadeh, M.; Lombardi, F. Design of sequential circuits by quantum-dot cellular automata. Microelectron. J. 2007, 38, 525-537.
- [13] Alamdar, H.; Ardeshir, G.; Gholami, M. Using Universal Nand-nor-inverter Gate to Design D-latch and D Flip-flop in Quantum-dot Cellular Automata Nanotechnology. Int. J. Eng. 2021, 34, 1710-1717.
- [14] Iwai, H. End of the scaling theory and Moore's law. In Proceedings of the 2016 16th International Workshop on Junction Technology (IWJT), Shanghai, China, 9-10 May 2016; pp. 1-4.
- [15] Amirzadeh, Z.; Gholami, M. Selective counter design in quantum-dot cellular automata nanotechnology. Concurr. Comput. Pract. Exp. 2022, 34, e6798.
- [16] Goswami, M.; Mondal, A.; Mahalat, M.H.; Sen, B.; Sikdar, B.K. An efficient clocking scheme for quantum-dot cellular automata. Int. J. Electron. Lett. 2020, 8, 83-96.
- [17] Jeon, J.-C. Low-complexity QCA universal shift register design using multiplexer and D flip-flop based on electronic correlations. J. Supercomput. 2020, 76, 6438-6452.